

THE IMPACT OF BUDGET POLICY ON HARMFUL SUBSTANCES EMITTED INTO THE ATMOSPHERE

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Abstract. *This article identifies and evaluates the impact of budget policy on the volume of harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere. The regional impact of local budget expenditures on atmospheric pollution across provinces has been analyzed using a Fixed-effects panel regression model. Based on this, the specific characteristics of green budget policy have been systematized. Scientific conclusions and recommendations have been developed based on the conducted research.*

Keywords: *green budget, climate change, harmful gases, green expenditures, energy efficiency, renewable energy.*

Introduction

One of the priority directions of the green economy is to reduce the volume of harmful substances emitted into the atmosphere. The emergence of harmful substances emitted into the atmosphere is directly related to the industrialization and development of the economy. It is known from the world economy that as economies develop, the volume of waste from production sectors also increases. As a result, the volume of harmful substances also grows.

In many countries, various fiscal policy instruments are used to regulate harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere. The aim is not only to regulate the volume of harmful gases but also to set certain limits on their volume. In our research, we focus on studying the impact of fiscal policy on the volume of harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere. It should be noted that a number of studies have been conducted in global science on this topic.

Literature Review

In a study conducted by K. Bletsas et al., scientific conclusions are formed based on panel data. It analyzes trends such as economic growth, government expenditures, and central bank independence in 95 countries from 1998-2019. It is substantiated that economic growth and government expenditures are factors that increase the volume of harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere. Additionally, it is noted that if institutional conditions (efficiency, central bank independence, and transparency) reflect positive trends, this negative situation can be mitigated. Based on this, the importance of institutional quality in evaluating the environmental impact of fiscal and monetary policy is highlighted [1].

S. Li et al., in their joint study, examine the impact of tax and budget policy on trends in BRICS countries from 1990-2019. While budget expenditures lead to increased atmospheric pollution, strict tax policy plays an important role in ensuring environmental sustainability. Therefore, renewable energy and the stringency of environmental policy are key factors in reducing carbon emissions. It is substantiated that fiscal policy, especially through tax revenues to the state budget, is effective as a tool against atmospheric pollution and can reduce the impact of government expenditures on pollution [2].

In an analysis conducted jointly by S. Li and co-authors, panel regression models are developed based on data from manufacturing enterprises. Their scientific conclusions note that green fiscal policy is an important financial policy in reducing carbon emissions into the atmosphere. Based on this study, the following financing directions of financial policy are prioritized for ensuring environmental sustainability: favorable financial subsidies and loans, development of environmental technologies through R&D investments, and expansion of instruments aimed at increasing energy efficiency. Overall, in prioritizing the directions of fiscal policy strictly aimed at environmental sustainability, these three aspects are distinguished [3].

In our opinion, improving the characteristic of fiscal policy aimed at environmental sustainability is relevant. Here, determining and evaluating the impact of fiscal policy on the amount of harmful gases emitted into the atmosphere is of great importance. Therefore, developing scientific proposals and recommendations aimed at optimizing the impact of fiscal policy is not an exaggeration.

F. Nurfatriani et al., in their joint study, analyze Indonesia's forest-related fiscal policy. This research forms scientific conclusions aimed at improving forest conservation priorities. It notes that the current fiscal policy does not encourage forest conservation practices. The inclination of local authorities toward income from deforestation exacerbates environmental consequences. They propose financial incentives for forest conservation and fiscal assessment of environmental efficiency. Based on this, the idea of developing green fiscal policy is promoted [4].

L. Atílio et al., in their joint scientific research, analyze the relationship between fiscal policy and deforestation. Government expenditures on infrastructure and road construction lead to deforestation. In countries with high institutional control and transparency, fiscal policy serves forest conservation. They propose preserving natural capital, green subsidies, and recommendations aimed at reducing deformation in green fiscal policy [5].

Analysis and Results

In order to study these scientific problems, we attempt to analyze the impact of tax and budget policy indicators on atmospheric pollution. Based on this, we analyze the impact of tax revenues and budget expenditures trends on atmospheric pollution across regions from 2017-2024. For this, we focus on analyzing panel data using the Stata software package.

First, we examine the trends in the impact of budget policy indicators on atmospheric pollution. To analyze panel data, we need to select one of the Fixed effects or Random Effects models. Here, we select the superior model by conducting the Hausman test.

Table 1 presents the Hausman test results where $\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$, i.e., the p-value is less than 1% probability, serving as a basis for selecting the Fixed Effects model. The selection of this model reflects that individual effects and related variables are correlated. Therefore, the selection of this model allows determining and evaluating the impact of fiscal policy on atmospheric pollution across regions and years.

Table 1. Hausman Test Results for Fixed Effects and Random Effects Models

	Coefficients		(b-B)	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	(b)	(B)		
	fe	re	Difference	Std. err.
Economic expenditures	-.0094222	-.0116056	.0021835	.002311

Social expenditures	-.0076412	-.0102343	.0025931	.0027897
Central investments	.0098643	.0130395	-.0031752	.0024309
Government expenditures	.0289692	.060821	-.0318518	.0047037
Non-tax expenditures	.0956689	.2390277	-.1433588	.0463251
Other expenditures	.0092018	-.0077467	.0169485	.0082523
b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from xtreg.				
B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from xtreg.				
Test of H0:	Difference in coefficients not systematic			
$\chi^2(9) = (b-B)'[(V_b - V_B)^{-1}](b-B) = 74.20$				
Prob > $\chi^2 = 0.0000$				

First, we examine the general trends using this model. Table 2 reflects the trends in the emission of harmful substances polluting the atmosphere in the context of budget policy. The Fixed-effects panel regression model presented in this analysis indicates that budget policy does not have a high impact. Specifically, the R^2 (within) = 0.1001 shows that the selected budget indicators explain the level of atmospheric pollution to a degree of 10%. Additionally, most selected indicators do not have a statistically significant impact.

Only the increase in economic expenditures is observed to reduce the level of atmospheric pollution. This trend likely increases the probability that budget economic expenditures are directed toward green approaches. The remaining budget indicators, lacking statistically significant impact, indicate that the direct impact of budget policy is negligible.

Table 2. Analysis of Budget Policy Impact on Atmospheric Pollution Using Fixed-effects Model

Fixed-effects (within) regression	Number of obs	112	Number of groups	14
R-squared:	Obs per group:		Group variable:	худуд
Within = 0.1001	min	8	F(6,13)	22.45
Between = 0.2342	avg	8.0	Prob > F	0.0000
Overall = 0.1282	max	8	corr(u_i, Xb)	0.2928

Economic expenditures	Coefficient	Std. err.	t	P>t	[95% conf. interval]
Social expenditures	-.0094222	.00432	-2.18	0.048	[-.018755, -.0000893]
Central investments	-.0076412	.0053658	-1.42	0.178	[-.0192334, .0039509]
Government expenditures	.0098643	.0079584	1.24	0.237	[-.0073287, .0270573]
Non-tax expenditures	.0289692	.0371463	0.78	0.449	[-.0512805, .1092188]
Other expenditures	.0956689	.058154	1.65	0.124	[-.0299652, .2213031]
Economic expenditures	.0092018	.0128665	0.72	0.487	[-.0185946, .0369983]
_cons	70.21251	5.168334	13.59	0.000	[59.047, 81.37801]
sigma_u	100.37111				

sigma_e	19.29738	
rho	.96435361	(fraction of variance due to u_i)

In our opinion, certain complexities are evident in the implementation of budget policy based on green approaches in our country. The budget policy does not have a stable impact on the change in the volume of harmful substances polluting the atmosphere. Therefore, we focus on examining the impact of budget policy across regions and years. The aim is to identify and evaluate the trends in regional characteristics of the budget. Additionally, we attempt to identify trends across years.

Table 3. Analysis of Budget Policy Impact on Atmospheric Pollution Across Regions and Years Using Fixed-effects Model

Fixed-effects (within) regression	Number of obs	112	Number of groups	14
R-squared:	Obs per group:		Group variable:	ҳудуд
Within = 0.5960	min	8	F(5,13)	-
Between = 0.6620	avg	8.0	Prob > F	-
Overall = 0.6010	max	8	corr(u_i, Xb)	0.6021

Atmospheric Pollution	Coefficient	std. err.	z	P>z	[95% conf. interval]
Economic expenditures	-.0476235	.0194455	-2.45	0.029	-.089633 - .005614
Region#c.Economic expenditures					
Andijan	.0366336	.0046976	7.80	0.000	.026485 .0467822
Bukhara	-.0282424	.0013883	-20.34	0.000	-.0312417 -.0252431
Jizzakh	.1000285	.0082929	12.06	0.000	.0821129 .1179442
Qashqadaryo	.0354316	.0153335	2.31	0.038	.0023057 .0685576
Navoiy	.0305339	.0024089	12.68	0.000	.0253297 .0357381
Namangan	.0407408	.011766	3.46	0.004	.0153218 .0661598
Samarkand	.0358593	.0082947	4.32	0.001	.0179396 .0537789
Surkhandarya	.0470814	.0118095	3.99	0.002	.0215685 .0725944
Sirdaryo	-.0426591	.00701	-6.09	0.000	-.0578033 -.0275149
Tashkent province	.1940322	.0067279	28.84	0.000	.1794974 .208567
Fergana	.0168623	.0036494	4.62	0.000	.0089783 .0247462
Khorezm	.0289161	.0064764	4.46	0.001	.0149247 .0429076
Tashkent city	.0398234	.0143886	2.77	0.016	.0087386 .0709081
Social expenditures					

Central investments	.0000977	.0031347	0.03	0.976	-.0066744	.0068698
Government expenditures	-.0009145	.0054721	-0.17	0.870	-.0127362	.0109072
Non-tax expenditures	.0140178	.0288748	0.49	0.635	-.0483625	.0763981
Other expenditures	.1467204	.1124105	1.31	0.214	-.0961277	.3895684
_cons	.0011052	.0100757	0.11	0.914	-.020662	.0228725
Economic expenditures	56.26814	10.22052	5.51	0.000	34.18804	78.34823
Atmospheric Pollution						
2017	.1427568	.1552494	0.92	0.358	-.1615264	.44704
2018	-.0122079	.0519134	-0.24	0.814	-.1139562	.0895405
2019	.0933437	.0503443	1.85	0.064	-.0053292	.1920166
2020	.002646	.0143138	0.18	0.853	-.0254086	.0307006
2021	-.0158055	.011614	-1.36	0.174	-.0385686	.0069575
2022	-.0262638	.0136708	-1.92	0.055	-.0530581	.0005305
2023	-.0072275	.0068683	-1.05	0.293	-.0206892	.0062342
2024	-.0056214	.008552	-0.66	0.511	-.022383	.0111402
sigma_u	81.347717					
sigma_e	13.953056					
rho	.97142046	(fraction of variance due to u_i)				

In Table 3, the budget's economic expenditures have a statistically significant impact on atmospheric pollution in the context of regional development trends. In addition to the overall impact coefficient of $-.0476235$, the impact coefficient for each region can be examined. Based on this, we were able to form the following scientific conclusions. These conclusions are developed without considering the interactive additional main impact ($\beta_0 = -.0476235$):

First, in Andijan, Jizzakh, Qashqadaryo, Navoiy, Namangan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Tashkent province, Fergana, Khorezm, and Tashkent city, local budget economic expenditures are leading to an increase in the volume of harmful substances polluting the atmosphere.

Second, in Bukhara and Sirdaryo provinces, local budget economic expenditures are leading to a decrease in atmospheric pollution.

In our opinion, in most local budgets, economic expenditures are leading to increased atmospheric pollution. Therefore, it is necessary to note that strengthening the role of local budgets in reducing atmospheric pollution is advisable.

Figure 1. Analysis of the Impact of Budget Economic Expenditures on Atmospheric Pollution from 2017-2024

From Figure 1, it is evident that the impact of budget policy has changed over the years. In particular, in 2017 and 2019, budget economic expenditures led to increased atmospheric pollution. In 2018 and 2020-2022, the impact indicates a decrease in pollution levels. In 2023-2024, it is necessary to emphasize the neutralization of the statistical impact on pollution. In general, it can be seen that budget economic expenditures have an unstable impact on atmospheric pollution but do not sharply increase it.

Continuing our research, we focus on studying the impact of tax policy on atmospheric pollution. Here, we attempt to develop the econometric models and tests used above based on tax indicators.

First, we examine the trends in the impact of tax policy indicators on atmospheric pollution. To analyze panel data, we need to select one of the Fixed effects or Random Effects models. Here, we select the superior model by conducting the Hausman test.

Table 4. Hausman Test Results for Fixed Effects and Random Effects Models

	Coefficients		(b-B)	sqrt(diag(V_b-V_B))
	(b)	(B)		
	fe	re	Difference	Std. err.
Profit tax	.0214196	.0221632	-.0007436	.0017828
Turnover tax	-.039374	-.0260039	-.0133701	.0085834
Personal income tax	-.0445446	-.0521299	.0075853	.0017237
Excise tax	.0209193	.0288412	-.0079219	.0014267
Property tax	.0250461	.0286612	-.0036151	.0034537
Land tax	.0306582	.021825	.0088331	.0034978

Subsoil use tax	.0266953	.0043605	.0223348	.0086002
Water resource tax	.5446653	.7449532	-.2002879	.0413862
Other income	-.0456478	-.0502769	.0046291	.0047144
b = Consistent under H0 and Ha; obtained from xtreg.				
B = Inconsistent under Ha, efficient under H0; obtained from xtreg.				
Test of H0:	Difference in coefficients not systematic			
chi2(9) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^(-1)](b-B) = 38.88				
Prob > chi2 = 0.0000				

Table 4 presents the Hausman test results where Prob > chi2 = 0.0000, i.e., the p-value is less than 1% probability, serving as a basis for selecting the Fixed Effects model. The selection of this model reflects that individual effects and related variables are correlated. Additionally, systematic differences exist in the Random Effects model. Therefore, the selection of this model allows determining and evaluating the impact of fiscal policy on atmospheric pollution across regions and years.

Table 5. Analysis of Tax Policy Impact on Atmospheric Pollution Using Fixed Effects Panel Regression Model

Fixed-effects (within) regression	Number of obs	112	Number of groups	14
R-squared:	Obs per group:		Group variable:	ҳудуд
Within = 0.4248	min	8	F(9,89)	7.30
Between = 0.7017	avg	8.0	Prob > chi2	0.0000
Overall = 0.6020	max	8	corr(u_i, X)	0.6548

Atmospheric Pollution	Coefficient	std. err.	z	P>z	[95% conf. interval]
Profit tax	.0214196	.0180038	1.19	0.237	-.0143535 .0571927
Turnover tax	-.039374	.0204316	-1.93	0.057	-.0799711 .001223
Personal income tax	-.0445446	.0076486	-5.82	0.000	-.0597422 -.029347
Excise tax	.0209193	.0113394	1.84	0.068	-.0016119 .0434506
Property tax	.0250461	.0173044	1.45	0.151	-.0093374 .0594296
Land tax	.0306582	.0226753	1.35	0.180	-.0143972 .0757135
Subsoil use tax	.0266953	.0515715	0.52	0.606	-.0757762 .1291668
Water resource tax	.5446653	.1153153	4.72	0.000	.3155363 .7737944
Other income	-.0456478	.0161088	-2.83	0.006	-.0776556 -.01364
_cons	73.108	4.972537	14.70	0.000	63.22768 82.98833
sigma_u	85.186285				
sigma_e	15.685183				
rho	.9672086	(fraction of variance due to u_i)			

F test that all $u_i=0$: $F(13, 89) = 87.98$	Prob > F = 0.0000
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Based on the model data in Table 5, we were able to develop the following scientific conclusions in general:

1. Personal income tax (-0.0445 , $p=0.000$) and other incomes (-0.0456 , $p=0.006$) can be seen to serve in reducing atmospheric pollution. It can be assumed that these types of taxes lead to more efficient use of natural resources.

2. Turnover tax limits the resource consumption and waste generation of business entities, making it significant.

3. The tax on water resources (0.5447 , $p=0.000$) is statistically significant and has a strong positive impact. This may be explained by the abundance of water use and the increase in waste in water-related sectors.

4. Excise tax (0.0209 , $p=0.068$) also has a positive impact, meaning it increases atmospheric pollution. In our view, this may be related to the production and consumption of excise-taxed products (e.g., fuel) exacerbating atmospheric pollution.

5. The impact of profit tax, property tax, land tax, subsoil use tax, etc., is statistically insignificant.

Conclusion

In our opinion, improving the role of fiscal policy in increasing environmental sustainability and achieving efficient resource use is important. Considering that income and turnover taxes have a positive impact on the ecosystem, aligning them with environmentally oriented policy is advisable. In general, fiscal policy has a noticeable importance in the emission of harmful substances polluting the atmosphere. Here, the role of tax policy should be emphasized separately.

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